

MUL+IPLIERS

WHITE BOOK

H2020 Coordination and Support Actions – (CSA)

MULTIPLIERS – Multiplayers Partnerships to ensure meaningful engagement with Science and Society

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Index of acronyms and abbreviations

D	Deliverable
GA	Grant Agreement
OSC	Open Science Community
OSS	Open-School Science
SO	Specific Objective
SSI	Socio-scientific issue
TLS	Teaching-Learning Sequence
WP	Work package

Consortium Partners

Organisation	Acronym	Country
University of Bonn	UBO	Germany
University of Cyprus	UCY	Cyprus
Autonomous University of Barcelona	UAB	Spain
University of Ljubljana	UL	Slovenia
Umeå University	UMU	Sweden
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1 Executive summary

This white book presents the final recommendations and guidelines from the MULTIPLIERS project, directed at practitioners and policymakers. Its main objective is to support the successful integration of open-schooling practices across diverse geographical, cultural, and economic contexts to ensure accessible, high-quality science education for all.

Through this white book, readers will find examples of complex socio-scientific issues tackled in the MULTIPLIERS project, providing valuable insights for anyone interested in initiating similar open-schooling projects.

The project advances an operational definition of Open Schooling, aligning with three core objectives: community impact, pedagogical impact, and scientific impact, with a strong emphasis on foundational values.

The primary goal of the project is to expand science learning opportunities by promoting cooperative partnerships and establishing Open Science Communities (OSCs). Specifically, it aims to (1) enhance students' interest in science, boost self-efficacy in science learning, and raise awareness of science careers by embedding real-life, open-school science learning projects in collaboration with science professionals and media experts into education; and (2) develop analytical and critical thinking skills in students, families, and the broader community to empower problem-solving and innovation.

Drawing on best practices in Open Schooling and the needs identified in partner countries, the MULTIPLIERS consortium has created a practical framework for implementing project activities through a structured teaching and learning sequence (TLS) comprising three phases:

Phase 1

Identifying and exploring socio-scientific issues (SSIs) relevant to the local community.

Phase 2

Engaging in an Open-School Science learning project (OSS).

Phase 3

Students acting as multipliers.

For each phase of the TLS, this white book outlines specific recommendations and guidelines.

In addition, the MULTIPLIERS project has developed a sustainability model designed to promote long-term collaboration between schools and external partner organizations. This model supports the ongoing integration of authentic science education into schools by establishing networks that connect formal education with real-world scientific expertise. The sustainability model rests on five key pillars: Communication, Coordination, Collaboration, Costs, and the Collection of Materials.

2 Background

Modern societies face complex challenges such as environmental sustainability and the promotion of healthy lifestyles. According to UNESCO's Science Report: Towards 2030 (2016), science plays a critical role in achieving Agenda 2030, which focuses on sustainable development. However, trust in scientific findings is in decline—an urgent issue for our times (Iyengar & Massey, 2019). The MULTIPLIERS project aims to counter this trend by addressing its root causes, using Open Schooling as a foundational framework. The project seeks to transform schools into innovative, open hubs for new ideas, practices, and scientific exploration, creating spaces within communities that encourage open, inclusive, and inquiry-based learning on science-related issues that directly impact people's daily lives.

This transformation is achieved by building partnerships ("Open Science Communities", OSCs) that connect schools with families, civil society organizations, informal education providers, policymakers, media, industry, and diverse scientific institutions across six EU countries—Cyprus, Germany, Italy, Slovenia, Spain, and Sweden—each representing different geographical and economic contexts.

Within these OSCs, socio-scientific issues (SSIs) relevant to each community are identified, and real-life projects are co-created and implemented in schools. These projects incorporate interactions with science professionals, inquiry-based learning, and hands-on experiences in authentic settings and workplaces. A key aspect of the project's Teaching-Learning Sequences (TLSs) is to develop students as knowledge "multipliers": after participating in an open-school science

project, students share their insights and experiences on the selected SSI with their families, peers, and local communities through communication formats of their own design.

By embedding such open-schooling projects into science education, the MULTIPLIERS project aims to increase students' interest in science, enhance their self-efficacy in learning science, and expand their awareness of science-related career paths. This addresses a concerning trend highlighted in policy reports regarding students' declining interest in science professions, and the importance of fostering enthusiasm for science learning (e.g., Chi & Wang, 2023; Hamlyn et al., 2024; OECD, 2016, 2017). By engaging students in real-world challenges and SSIs and encouraging them to practice argumentation and decision-making, the project also aims to foster their analytical and critical thinking skills.

Building on the outcomes generated by the MULTIPLIERS project, this white book compiles final recommendations and guidelines for practitioners and policymakers to support the implementation of successful open-schooling initiatives. The preparation of this white book was a collaborative effort among all project partners, with particular contributions from the leaders of Work Packages 2, 3, 4, and 5. Its primary goal is to facilitate the adaptation of Open Schooling into educational contexts across varied geographical, cultural, and economic settings, promoting accessible, high-quality science education for all. Consideration of differences across countries and social contexts has further enhanced the adaptability and potential for international adoption and ongoing development of these activities.

3 MULTIPLIERS Themes Representing Complex Socio-Scientific Issues

What is a complex socio-scientific issue that is worth studying in a local setting? Below we give a brief description of each of the themes representing complex socio-scientific issues and were implemented as part of the MULTIPLIERS project. This might be helpful for anyone interested in starting a project similar to the one presented here.

Vaccination

Vaccination represents a pivotal socio-scientific issue, particularly in the context of global health and pandemic preparedness. The challenge revolves around ensuring widespread access to vaccines while addressing public concerns about safety and efficacy. With the emergence of new infectious diseases and the resurgence of preventable illnesses, vaccination programs are crucial in protecting public health. However, vaccine hesitancy and misinformation pose significant barriers. This theme explores the balance between individual choice and community health benefits, emphasizing the importance of informed decision-making and scientific literacy. By examining the complexities surrounding vaccination, students engage in critical discussions about public health strategies, ethical considerations, and the role of science in society.

Antimicrobial-resistance

Antimicrobial resistance (AMR) presents a critical socio-scientific issue, threatening the effectiveness of antibiotics and other antimicrobial agents. The misuse and overuse of these drugs in healthcare and agriculture accelerate the evolution of resistant strains, undermining efforts to treat common infections. This theme highlights the urgent need for global cooperation to develop new treatments, implement stewardship programs, and educate the public about responsible antibiotic use. Students explore the intersection of science, policy, and ethics in combating AMR, fostering an understanding of how scientific innovation and behavioral change are essential in addressing this global health crisis.

Air pollution

Air pollution is a pervasive socio-scientific issue with significant health and environmental impacts. Rapid industrialization, urbanization, and increased vehicle emissions contribute to deteriorating air quality, affecting millions worldwide. This theme examines the sources and consequences of air pollution, including respiratory illnesses, climate change, and ecosystem damage. Students investigate measures to mitigate air pollution, such as adopting cleaner technologies, implementing stricter regulations, and promoting public awareness. By engaging with this topic, students develop critical thinking skills and a deeper understanding of the interconnectedness of human activities and environmental health, highlighting the need for sustainable solutions.

Biodiversity and ecosystem services

Biodiversity and ecosystem services are fundamental to the health and resilience of our planet. The loss of biodiversity due to human activities such as deforestation, pollution, and climate change disrupts ecosystem functions that provide essential services like pollination, water purification, and climate regulation. This theme addresses the socio-scientific dilemma of balancing human development with the conservation of natural habitats. Students explore the value of biodiversity, the threats it faces, and strategies for sustainable management. Through this inquiry, they gain insights into the complex relationships between ecosystems and human well-being, emphasizing the necessity of preserving biodiversity for future generations.

Clean water and sanitation

Access to clean water and sanitation is a critical socio-scientific issue that affects public health, economic development, and environmental sustainability. In many regions, water scarcity, pollution, and inadequate infrastructure hinder access to safe drinking water and proper sanitation. This theme explores the challenges and solutions related to ensuring universal access to clean water and sanitation. Students examine the impact of waterborne diseases, the role of water management practices, and innovative technologies for water purification and conservation. By addressing this issue, students learn about the importance of integrated water resource management and the role of science and policy in achieving global water security.

Biodiversity and agriculture

With a growing world population, the question of how sufficient access to healthy food can be guaranteed for all people becomes increasingly urgent. At the same time, scaling up food production has come at the cost of environmentally harmful practices that accelerate biodiversity loss through e. g., habitat loss and fragmentation, erosion, or chemical run-off that pollutes nature. To illustrate the dilemma, agriculture is used as an example to show the oftentimes conflicting aims of – on the one hand – using land capacities for producing food, and – on the other hand – using land capacities for conserving biodiversity.

Forest use vs. forest protection

This theme addresses the complex balance between human needs and ecological preservation. As global demands escalate, forests face dual pressures: resource extraction for societal needs and conservation to maintain biodiversity and ecosystem stability. This socio-scientific dilemma mirrors broader environmental challenges, highlighting the urgent need for sustainable practices. By exploring this theme, students confront pressing questions about reconciling economic development with environmental conservation. This inquiry fosters critical thinking and informed decision-making, emphasizing the imperative of holistic approaches to ensure the long-term health of forests and ecosystems amid growing human demands.

4 MULTIPLIERS Operational Definition

The MULTIPLIERS project proposes an operational definition of Open Schooling for use in the project. Our Open Schooling approach integrates three key objectives—community impact, pedagogical impact and scientific impact—while explicitly highlighting core values.

MULTIPLIERS operational definition of Open Schooling

Open Schooling is an educational perspective in which schools become open to society by bidirectionally collaborating with different institutions with the aim to:

- A** Improve community well-being by raising awareness and co-creating solutions to both personal and socially relevant problems that have a direct impact at a local level.
- B** Enrich the curricula and pedagogical repertoire of schools, by sharing different views and expertise from both educational and non-educational agents and institutions with the aim to promote students' meaningful learning and competence development.
- C** Give epistemic authority to all agents from within and outside of the school, specifically to the students and their families, by engaging them in sustained inquiry, knowledge creation, creative action, and dissemination on issues of relevance to the local community and beyond.

To do so, the projects and initiatives on Open Schooling take advantage of the knowledge, practices, visions, attitudes, resources, and values of all involved agents, empowering them to collectively transform society from a reflective and critical standpoint that focuses on sustainability, equity, social justice, and inclusion.

The operational definition also serves as a foundation for developing a common approach to establishing Open Science Communities and creating evaluation tools to assess their effectiveness.

5 MULTIPLIERS Objectives and Approach

The MULTIPLIERS project's main objective is to expand opportunities for science learning by fostering cooperation through learning partnerships and the establishment of Open Science Communities (OSCs).

Two specific objectives (SO) that can be found in the Grant Agreement (GA) were used to guide the development of the Teaching Learning Sequences (TLSs).

Specific objectives of OSCs

- To increase students' interest in science, self-efficacy for learning science, and their science career awareness by integrating real-life, open-school science learning projects with science professionals and media experts – including authentic settings and workplaces – into science education.
- To develop analytical and critical thinking competencies for students, families, and the wider community to enable problem solving and innovation. This is to be achieved through TLSs focusing on issues related to societal challenges and SSIs, inquiry learning, argumentation, collaboration, communication, and decision making.

These two SOs have been in focus during the development and implementation of TLSs and were evaluated using quantitative and qualitative methods. The data collection methods consisted of a validated questionnaire and semi-structured interviews with the participants to reflect on the MULTIPLIERS experience at the end of each implementation round.

Based on the review of existing good practices in Open Schooling and the identification of current needs in the partner countries, the consortium has developed an operational framework for implementing MULTIPLIERS activities and developing a TLS. It is structured in three phases (Fig. 1) and includes key concepts deriving from the operational definition of 'Open Schooling' and the SOs:

Figure 1. The MULTIPLIERS common approach.

Phase 1

Identification and exploration of socio-scientific issues (SSIs) of relevance to the local community

OSC members jointly design the teaching and learning activities. First, they identify and explore SSIs that are relevant to the local community. Next, the SSI is defined, and instruction is built around socio-scientific issues to provide awareness, develop students' interest in science and relevant competences (e.g., argumentation), and guide the development of the Open-schooling science learning project (OSS).

Common objectives of OSCs

- Co-design and enact interesting and challenging inter-disciplinary inquiry projects for school students to strengthen their analytical and critical thinking competencies, on issues of societal relevance;
- Create collaboration initiatives between schools and science professionals to broaden role models that are accessible to students and enrich their interests and career aspirations;
- Support students in their role as multipliers bringing their projects to their families and local communities by actively involving them in inquiry projects and by developing courses of action to reach wide audiences;
- Contribute to the development of guidelines and policy recommendations informing policy makers about the achievements and contributions of OSCs supporting schools in Europe.

It is important to point out that the OSCs respect the GDPR regulation and all national and EU ethical standards in relation to scientific research and educational activities with children, professionals and communities and that confidentiality is respected.

Phase 2

Engagement in the Open-school science learning project (OSS)

In this phase, the students explore the SSI relevant to the local community based on the instruction built in phase 1 and co-create solutions in collaboration with the OSC members. More specifically, they elaborate on the local challenges to be addressed and engage in the OSS to tackle the selected SSI, and build knowledge based on sustained inquiry. The students are actively engaged in authentic activities and scientific practices through interactions with experts and become involved in decision-making processes using evidence for their argumentation. Hence, the students collaborate with several stakeholders to explore different perspectives and improve their understanding while being involved in scientific practices (e.g., problem-based activities, collecting and analyzing data, modelling, argumentation).

Phase 3 Students acting as multipliers

In the last phase, students act as multipliers sharing their knowledge and communicate science to the wider public through Open Schooling events. Having gained first-hand experiences and an insight into inquiry-oriented practices and discussions, students become knowledge multipliers; they present, share, and deepen their knowledge and experiences in activities by actively involving their families and the wider community, through dedicated local events (e.g., open-school/local action days, citizen science activities) and communication media (e.g., exhibitions, social media channels, and video clips).

For each phase, the key concepts, design principles, and possible scaffolds to facilitate implementation are described in Tables 1, 2 & 3. It is important to note that the structure of this framework is not strictly sequential and that a circular process (i.e., iterative cycles) can occur within the phases. Hence, the duration of the TLS can last various weeks depending on the OSS project and the flexibility of the stakeholders involved.

In each OSC, open-schooling science learning projects are developed collaboratively with science experts in order to bring real-life cases to the students regarding contemporary challenges/socio-scientific issues (e.g., air pollution, biodiversity and ecosystem services, vaccination, forest use vs. forest protection, anti-microbial resistance, clean water and sanitation).

Key Concepts

Key Concepts derive from the operational definition of Open Schooling and the project's specific objectives. Key Concepts can be found in more than one phase of the framework (Figure 1). In addressing these concepts, we provide a list of corresponding Design Principles as described next.

Design Principles

The Design Principles are prescriptive statements to be used as “the basis for designing practical action concepts to achieve the defined practice goals” (Euler, 2017, p. 2) thus corresponding to the Key Concepts.

Scaffolds

The Scaffolds are possible strategies that can facilitate the implementation of educational actions. Examples of scaffolds that were successfully used during the project are provided in Tables 1, 2 & 3.

6 MULTIPLIERS Recommendations and Guidelines

This chapter describes recommendations and guidelines for each phase of the TLS.

Table 1. Phase 1: Identification & Exploration of socio-scientific issues of relevance to the local community

Key Concepts	Design Principles	Scaffolds
Raising awareness about socio-scientific issues	Build instruction around an SSI within a related teaching unit	Authentic media: Design activities using local authentic media related to the SSI. The authentic media can be newspaper/magazine articles, academic articles, videos, podcasts, social media posts, etc.
Personal and socially relevant / real-life problems	Identify scaffolds for students to make explicit connections to the curriculum	Brainstorming activities: Design brainstorming activities to help students retrieve prior knowledge such as mind mapping, matching activities and short quizzes using online tools.
Students' competence development (argumentation)	Identify scaffolds for students to engage in argumentation and allow them to navigate the social dimensions of the scientific issue	Debates, jigsaw groups, role-playing: The first step to organise a debate is to identify the different stakeholders and their perspectives in relation to the SSI. Then define a debate topic and find indicative authentic media to share with the students in their stakeholder groups/jigsaw groups. Prepare a scoring table to help students formulate a good/strong argument.
Science-society interactions of relevance to the community	Identify SSIs of local relevance and document each SSI, its relevance to the community and possible options for community action	Authentic media: Identify local authentic media related to the SSI to connect learning activities to the 'real world' in the local community. The local authentic media can be newspaper/magazine articles, academic articles, interviews with the local stakeholders, videos, podcasts, social media posts, etc.

<p>Focus on values, including social justice, sustainability, inclusion and equity</p>	<p>Ensure the participation of marginalised students with diverse identities in terms of race, gender, religion, SOE status</p>	<p>Role-playing and reflection activities: Design role-playing activities to support students' analysis of the different perspectives as they work toward identifying their own position on a controversial issue.</p>
<p>Students' interest in science</p>	<p>Highlight relevance to students' everyday life</p>	<p>Examples from everyday life: Include examples from everyday life in discussions with students when designing the teaching and learning activities (e.g., common misconceptions about the use of antibiotics).</p>

Table 2. Phase 2: Engagement in the Open-school science learning project

Key Concepts	Design Principles	Scaffolds
Documentation of the SSI and elaboration of the problem(s)/challenge(s) to be addressed	Representation of the problem(s), the relevant parameters and the key stakeholders that can facilitate change	<p>Direct Interaction with Experts: Allow direct interaction between students (+teachers) and experts from various scientific fields, to foster the documentation of the SSI and the elaboration of the problem(s)/challenge(s) to be addressed. This interaction also allows students to gain first hand research experience and insights into different science career options as well as an understanding of the day-to-day responsibilities and challenges of various professions.</p>
Co-creating solutions	Ensure continuity by providing the students with opportunities to reflect and prompt them to create possible solutions to the SSI	<p>Interdisciplinary and Holistic Learning: By combining different subject areas, such as science, social studies, and arts, students can gain a more comprehensive understanding of the SSI. This approach helps them see the interconnectedness of various disciplines and their relevance to addressing complex issues.</p> <p>Sustained Interaction with Professionals: While one-time visits and excursions are valuable, ongoing engagement with experts through a series of visits or a structured program over several weeks provides students with continuous exposure and more opportunities to explore different aspects of SSI and create possible solutions.</p>
Creative action	Prompt students to create possible solutions to the SSI using creativity	<p>Creative and Interactive Activities: Activities, such as designing new products, writing rap songs, and conducting debates, can be effective in capturing student interest. These activities allow students to express themselves in unique ways and made learning more enjoyable and engaging. These methods also cater to diverse learning styles.</p>

<p>Collaboration between educational and non-educational agents</p>	<p>Promote students' interaction with educational and non-educational agents and institutions</p>	<p>Expert Involvement and Community Engagement: Meeting researchers and professionals in authentic settings provides students with new and sometimes exclusive insights into real-world scientific work and inspires them to think critically about their own learning in the context of SSI. Community engagement, including interactions with families and local organizations, not only helps to disseminate knowledge about real problems/challenges to be addressed and raise awareness of the project's goals, but also motivates students to participate in project activities.</p>
<p>Students' science career awareness</p>	<p>Promote a meaningful interaction between experts and the students</p>	<p>Experiential Learning and Work Environment Exposure: By visiting authentic work environments and engaging in tasks performed by professionals, students gain a deeper understanding of what different careers entail. For instance, acting as researchers, doctors, or laboratory technicians helps students immerse themselves in the roles and understand the skills and knowledge required.</p> <p>Insights from Experts and Personal Stories: Through interactions with professionals, students are exposed to personal stories and career journeys that provide deeper insights into different professions. Experts share their experiences, challenges, and motivations, which helps students understand the diversity within career paths and the non-linear nature of professional growth. Hearing about the personal and professional lives of scientists, for example, helps students see the human side of these careers, making them more accessible and appealing, especially also for female students.</p> <p>Addressing Career Awareness at Different Ages: For younger students, the focus might be on sparking curiosity and providing a broad overview of science careers. Older students are given more detailed insights and opportunities to engage deeply with professionals, which helps them make more informed decisions about their future education and career paths.</p>

<p>Sustained inquiry and competence development (argumentation, critical thinking)</p>	<p>Active student engagement in authentic activities evaluating evidence and supporting claims</p>	<p>Engaging with Authentic Media: The use of authentic media involves students in critically analysing real articles or videos, which helps them develop the ability to discern trustworthy information and formulate well-founded arguments. Through this process, students practice filtering information and constructing arguments based on evidence, which is crucial for critical thinking.</p> <p>Structured Discussion Activities: Implementing structured activities such as debates, role-playing, and simulations encourage students to think critically about real-life scenarios. For example, students might read medical histories or inoculate bacteria in a lab setting, which prompts discussions about the related professional roles and responsibilities in dealing with SSI.</p>
<p>Students' self-efficacy for learning science</p>	<p>Promote students' ownership of their learning</p>	<p>Student Autonomy and Responsibility: Giving students autonomy and responsibility in their learning process foster students' interest. This includes work in groups, and taking charge of the working process and project results.</p>
<p>Knowledge construction and validation</p>	<p>Promote students' collaboration to build and also test knowledge</p>	<p>Collaboration and Teamwork: Encouraging collaboration among students and with external stakeholders allow students to work together, share ideas, and support each other, which not only improves their learning experience but also the development of essential skills like communication and teamwork.</p>
<p>Impact at local level</p>	<p>Sustain the OSS project with explicit connections to the local context</p>	<p>Engagement of Community Actors: Debates can serve as a powerful tool to connect educational activities to the local context and create community impact. Engaging in debates on real, community-relevant issues fosters active participation in democratic processes and deepens students' understanding of local concerns.</p>

<p>Focus on values, including social justice, sustainability, inclusion and equity</p>	<p>Ensure the participation of marginalised students with diverse identities in terms of race, gender, religion, SOE status.</p>	<p>Listening to Diverse Perspectives: Pop-up events at public places and similar activities allow students to encounter and critically evaluate different viewpoints. This exposure helps them understand the importance of considering multiple perspectives when forming arguments and making decisions. It also cultivates an environment where critical examination of ideas is encouraged, further strengthening their argumentation skills.</p>
<p>Students' interest in science</p>	<p>Conduct activities in an authentic context relating to the SSI</p>	<p>Hands-on and Inquiry-based Learning: Engaging students in practical experiments allows them to apply theoretical knowledge to real-world scenarios. This approach not only makes learning more tangible but also sparked curiosity and sustained interest.</p>
<p>Collaborative expertise exchange</p>	<p>Bring together specialists from different fields to enhance quality, relevance, and impact of educational resources</p>	<p>Incorporation of Diverse Expertise: Promote the exchange of knowledge and involve various experts in the development of resources. This includes targeted reviews (e.g., scientists for content accuracy, education specialists for quality, media experts for communication) and creating tools for others, such as school visit guides for STEM professionals or science briefs for teachers.</p>

Table 3. Phase 3: Students acting as multipliers

Key Concepts	Design Principles	Scaffolds
Knowledge dissemination	Promote the dissemination of the OSS project results through Open Schooling events	Students acting as multipliers: Students share their knowledge and communicate science to their families and the wider public through Open Schooling activities or events, such as science fairs, poster exhibitions, videos, social media and community debates. Educational posters, continuous video screenings, and multimedia presentations visually engage the audience and provide continuous learning opportunities.
Students' competence development (critical thinking, argumentation)	Promote the development of strategies to negotiate with the public about the controversial nature of the SSI	Events in public spaces: Events organized in public and easy accessible spaces like libraries and shopping malls allow public consultation, negotiation of popular ideas, fact-checking conspiracy theories and countering misinformation and disinformation.
Creative action	Disseminate the results of the OSS project through creative actions	Creative dissemination activities: Students can create and share their own articles, videos or games on the SSI to raise public awareness.
Students' competence development (Problem solving and argumentation)	Engage the students, families and the wider community in evidence-based argumentation	Personal engagement of students: Allow students to interact directly with experts from various fields. This engagement exposes students to decision-making processes and critical thought inherent in professional practices. By participating in multiplying activities that simulate real-life challenges, students learn to apply critical thinking in practical contexts. Such activities bridge the gap between theoretical knowledge and practical application, fostering deeper understanding and enhanced argumentation skills.

<p>Focus on values, including social justice, sustainability, inclusion and equity</p>	<p>Ensure the participation of marginalised people with diverse identities in terms of race, gender, religion, SOE status</p>	<p>Various locations and venues: Choose various locations and venues for the project's activities, including public and easily accessible spaces like libraries or shopping malls. These locations provided opportunities to reach diverse audiences, including marginalized people, engaging them in educational activities and increasing the impact and visibility of the students' initiatives. Similarly, community events, such as fairs and excursion trips can be utilized to reach various target groups.</p>
<p>Students' self-efficacy for learning science</p>	<p>Promote student-centered approach to foster students' ownership of their learning</p>	<p>Targeting audience: Let students decide for themselves which target audience they want to address with their activities and which methods they want to use.</p> <p>Designing multiplying activities: Students should be supported by their teachers, but especially by experts from OSCs (scientists, media experts, etc.) who provide their expertise, enriching the content and ensuring the accuracy of the information shared. Science communication experts can facilitate workshops and mini-trainings, helping students learn how to effectively disseminate scientific ideas to the public and to specific target groups. This collaboration with professionals from various fields ensures that the students' multiplying activities are well-informed and impactful.</p>

Impact at local level	Disseminate the results of the OSS project in the local community	<p>Public discussions and consultations: Debate activities and public consultations offer platforms for students to practice and refine their argumentation skills. The target audience for the multiplying can vary widely, including the general public, schoolmates, families, and the broader community. Family members and younger students at schools can also be targeted, ensuring a wide range of engagement across different age groups and community segments.</p>
Students' interest in science	Develop dissemination activities that are interesting and engaging	<p>Interesting and engaging multiplying activities: Outdoor activities and hands-on learning experiences as well as indoor exhibitions and presentations facilitate interactive discussions with a diverse audience, including family members and university students.</p>
Students' competence development	Provide opportunities for the students to reflect on the MULTIPLIERS activities	<p>Teacher facilitation and reflection: Teachers play a crucial role in facilitating these experiences and reflecting on their impact. They observe students' growth in confidence and self-efficacy and adjust their teaching strategies accordingly. This reflective practice ensures that self-efficacy development remains a central focus in educational planning and implementation.</p>

Expertise exchange among OSC experts

A key design principle for bridging schools with society is fostering the **exchange of expertise among OSC experts**, ensuring a knowledge-driven, high-quality approach. This goal is achieved by involving a diverse array of experts—teachers, researchers, industry professionals, informal learning providers, policymakers, civil society organizations, NGOs, and media—throughout all project phases. For example, Barcelona’s OSC brought together epidemiologists, computer scientists, teachers, local media, and students, each playing a role at different stages in developing teaching materials, implementing them in schools, and empowering students as knowledge multipliers. In this model, researchers helped identify core concepts, while teachers adapted these ideas into practical classroom activities. “Bridging positions” are vital for connecting scientists and industry with schools. In the Barcelona OSC, science education researchers served this role, facilitating collaboration and creating resources, such as an infographic to guide STEM professionals in fostering equitable student engagement.

Author: Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona

Meaningful interactions with local communities

A key design principle was **promoting meaningful interactions between students and local communities** to increase scientific understanding of sustainable water management and use and debunk common myths and fake news, encouraging good habits to protect water resources and safeguard the environment. The learning process was enriched by allowing students to directly engage with experts in the water sector, providing guidance for future career paths. Additionally, students were involved in peer training initiatives addressed to different age and target groups: this allowed them to be protagonists in creating their own scientific knowledge. As a result, they realize how science impacts on citizenship and they felt more motivated to share the acquired knowledge with people outside the school also in the framework of public events. Cooperation in this project was useful in establishing new contacts and defining formats that can be replicated and used to transfer knowledge on other topics, expanding the network and involving other stakeholders.

Author: IREN

Engaging with professionals in real-world contexts

A key design principle was **promoting meaningful interactions between experts and students**. The learning process was enriched by allowing students to directly engage with professionals in real-world contexts. Both teachers and experts emphasized the value of this interaction in authentic settings, noting that students showed increased interest and engagement in the topic of vaccination. Additionally, these experiences helped shape students' future career choices, highlighting the importance of integrating diverse professional contexts into science education. The collaboration within the OSC provided students with exposure to diverse professional environments, such as labs, research facilities, and media labs. Hands-on experiences offered students a concrete understanding of scientific careers and concepts, often inaccessible in traditional classrooms.

Author: University of Bonn

Dissemination through Open Schooling events

In Cyprus, where antibiotic consumption is among the highest in the EU, **promoting the dissemination of the OSS project results** on antimicrobial resistance (AMR) **through Open Schooling events** was crucial for raising public awareness. The local OSC (comprising chemists, biologists, industry pharmacists, health professionals from the Ministry of Health, a biology inspector from the Ministry of Education, and academics in medicine, epidemiology, and microbiology) joined forces to organize two awareness campaigns over consecutive years. Additionally, a group of MULTIPLIERS students participated in two science fairs, engaging visitors with materials and interactive activities they prepared, including quizzes, puzzles, flyers, role-play debates (featured in the WHO Campaign on AMR), board games, digital games, modeling activities, and memory games. Organizing and hosting these events empowered students to take ownership of their learning and creatively collaborate to share knowledge, ultimately enhancing their view of science as engaging, relevant, and informative through their partnerships with OSC experts.

Author: University of Cyprus

Hands-on, experiential learning

A key design principle was to **offer students experiential learning through hands-on activities in real-world environments**. To achieve this, an educational Marteloscope was established on the slopes of Šmarna Gora in Slovenia. Marteloscopes are designated forest plots where each tree's ecological and economic value is recorded, serving as training grounds for foresters, students, and the public. In a Marteloscope, participants can “become foresters,” engaging in field exercises to decide which trees to retain or remove based on various criteria. This experience fosters learning about biodiversity and forest ecosystem services. The Marteloscope was developed in collaboration with teachers from Šmartno pod Šmarno Goro Primary School, the Slovenian Forest Institute, the Slovenian Forest Service, the European Forest Institute, and the Faculty of Education at the University of Ljubljana.

Author: University of Ljubljana

Engagement with educational and community agents

By **engaging students in meetings with experts, families, and community members**, the teaching activities promoted interaction with both educational and community-based agents and institutions. The goal was to deepen students' ownership of learning by engaging them in authentic, forest-themed activities. Students visited a research institute, where they explored lab equipment and conducted hands-on forest product testing, which several students noted sparked a greater interest in science. As one student remarked, "It was fun to see what they were investigating; it was more than I could think of." Additionally, students participated in a forest excursion with a municipal biologist and conducted a community poll outside a local store, gathering insights on forest use. These experiences empowered students to take active ownership of their learning process.

Author: University of Umeå

7 MULTIPLIERS Sustainability Model

The MULTIPLIERS project has developed a sustainability model aimed at fostering long-term collaboration between schools and out-of-school partner institutions. This model ensures that authentic science education can be continuously integrated into schools by establishing a network that bridges formal education and real-world (scientific) expertise.

The model is built on five **key components**—Communication, Coordination, Collaboration, Costs, and Collection of Materials. Each component addresses critical factors required to maintain and expand partnerships:

Communication ensures that all stakeholders—students, teachers, scientists, and community members—are kept informed and engaged through both digital and in-person interactions.

Coordination emphasizes the importance of structured management, diversity in partnerships, and alignment with local and national educational goals.

Collaboration focuses on transparency, shared responsibilities, and the active involvement of all participants in decision-making processes, fostering a culture of mutual learning and support.

Costs encourages the exploration of diverse funding sources, including public-private partnerships and grants, to secure financial sustainability.

Collection of materials ensures that educational resources are accessible, up-to-date, and adaptable, enabling teachers to integrate them into classrooms effectively.

Figure 2. The MULTIPLIERS sustainability model (“5 Co-Model”).

Sustaining partnerships for Open Schooling and authentic, meaningful science education

This sustainability model (“Multipliers 5 Co-Model”; described in detail in deliverable D7.2 Report describing the Sustainability Model for Multipliers OSCs) aims to create long-lasting networks that not only enhance science education but also address broader societal issues by encouraging meaningful interactions between educational institutions and science professionals. The model provides practical guidelines that can be adapted to different local contexts, ensuring its relevance and impact across diverse educational settings.

Key Recommendations from the 5 Co-Model for Sustainable Networks

Communication

- Inform other people about the network and interact regularly with all the network members by using multiple activities and interventions.
- Make sure you reach and include all the different partners by using the most efficient communication strategy and appropriate language.

Coordination

- Foster partner diversity and cultivate local partnerships to leverage community resources and insights, ensuring the project is grounded in local needs and perspectives.
- Implement clear network and management structures and adopt robust resource management strategies to maximize the effective use of financial, human, and material resources.
- Develop a clear strategy for the network that aligns with national education goals and societal needs.

Collaboration

- Foster and encourage participation through transparency and clear roles/responsibilities.
- Promote a culture of peer feedback and mutual support among partners to enhance collaboration, quality and collective learning throughout the project.
- Actively involve all stakeholders, including students, teachers, parents, industry partners, and policymakers, in exchange and decision-making processes.

Costs

- Ensure financial resources by using different funding strategies and exploring diverse funding sources, including public-private partnerships, grants, and community support, to ensure financial stability.

Collection of materials

- Guarantee the adequate dissemination and use of materials by making them easily accessible and by using different support structures.
- Implement continuous teacher training programs within the network to equip educators with the skills and knowledge needed to effectively use and adapt available materials.

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9 Appendix

MULTIPLIERS Policy Brief series

How can an operational definition of Open Schooling help us in transforming society?

Authors: MULTIPLIERS consortium

Modern societies are confronted with complex challenges, such as environmental protection and the promotion of healthy living. However, trust in scientific findings is declining—an urgent issue of our time. MULTIPLIERS has set an ambitious goal to reverse this trend by addressing the problem at its roots, using the concept of Open Schooling as its guiding framework. This document outlines the project's objectives and provides a brief overview of our operational definition of Open Schooling.

The MULTIPLIERS project, building on the strengths of an international consortium consisting of eight Beneficiaries, aims to initiate a process that helps schools' transition into innovative hubs for new ideas, practices, and scientific approaches. The project seeks to create spaces within the communities where the Beneficiaries operate, fostering open, inclusive, and inquiry-based

learning on scientific issues that impact citizens' daily lives. This was accomplished by establishing partnerships ('Open Science Communities') that bring together schools, families, civil society organizations, informal education providers, policymakers, media, industry, and a wide range of scientific institutions across six diverse EU countries—Cyprus, Germany, Italy, Slovenia, Spain, and Sweden—each with different geographical and economic contexts.

The MULTIPLIERS project offers a practical definition of Open Schooling for use in next phases of the project. In light of the above, we propose an Open Schooling approach that integrates three key objectives—community impact, pedagogical impact and scientific impact—while explicitly highlighting core values.

Open Schooling is an educational perspective in which schools become open to society by bidirectionally collaborating with different institutions with the aim to:

- a. Improve community well-being by raising awareness and co-creating solutions to both personal and socially relevant problems that have a direct impact at a local level.
- b. Enrich the curricula and pedagogical repertoire of schools, by sharing different views and expertise from both educational and non-educational agents and institutions with the aim to promote students' meaningful learning and competence development.
- c. Give epistemic authority to all agents from within and outside of the school, specifically to the students and their families, by engaging them in sustained inquiry, knowledge creation, creative action, and dissemination on issues of relevance to the local community and beyond.

To do so, the projects and initiatives on Open Schooling take advantage of the knowledge, practices, visions, attitudes, resources, and values of all involved agents, empowering them to collectively transform society from a reflective and critical standpoint that focuses on sustainability, equity, social justice, and inclusion.

The operational definition also serves as a foundation for developing a unified approach to establishing Open Science Communities and creating evaluation tools to assess their effectiveness.

The MULTIPLIERS project is also a call to policy makers and other professionals in education to take concrete steps to promote open schooling. [The ESD for 2030 roadmap](#) (UNESCO, 2020) states in priority area 1:

“Education policy makers, in collaboration with other ministries, civil society organizations, private companies, and academia, should develop policies to systematically strengthen synergistic relationships between formal, non-formal and informal education and learning.” (p. 26).

Conclusion

This policy brief offers an operational definition of Open Schooling to guide the implementation of the MULTIPLIERS project. We define Open Schooling as an educational approach where schools engage with society, integrating three core objectives—community impact, pedagogical impact, and scientific impact—while highlighting the knowledge, practices, visions, attitudes, resources, and values of all participants. This empowers them to collaboratively transform society with a reflective and critical focus on sustainability, equity, social justice, and inclusion.

The proposed operational definition of Open Schooling provides guidance to policy makers on how to integrate Education for Sustainable Development into all policies that explicitly address the achievement of the Sustainable Development Goals, which are at the heart of the complex challenges targeted by the project. The operational definition outlines how schools can open up to society by working bidirectionally with different educational and non-educational agents and institutions to empower all to engage in meaningful and transformative learning.

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Making school science relevant to real-world challenges through Open Schooling Science learning projects

Authors: MULTIPLIERS consortium

The MULTIPLIERS project aims to expand opportunities for science learning by fostering collaboration between students, schools, families, local communities, civil society organizations, informal learning providers, universities, the media, policy makers and industry. Here we provide information on how in Open Science Communities (OSCs) that have been established in the project countries—Germany, Cyprus, Spain, Slovenia, Sweden and Italy—collaboration and authentic science learning can be fostered. [GreenComp](#), the European sustainability competence framework, published in 2022, highlights the importance of encouraging learners to act at individual and collective level to shape sustainable futures. This demands teachers, schools and policy makers to make change happen. A plethora of stakeholders at local level must work together to shape and achieve global transformations for a more sustainable planet. OSCs provide local communities with a space for open, inclusive and inquiry-based learning on science issues that have an impact on citizens' lives.

In each OSC, open-schooling science (OSS) learning projects were developed collaboratively with science professionals to bring real-life cases to the students regarding contemporary challenges/ socio-scientific issues. Students collaborated

with several stakeholders to explore different perspectives and improve their understanding while being involved in scientific practices (e.g., problem-based activities, collecting and analysing data, modelling, argumentation). Having gained first-hand experiences and an insight into inquiry-oriented practices in authentic learning environments, students became knowledge multipliers; they presented and shared their knowledge and experiences in multiplying activities by actively involving their families and the wider community, through dedicated local events (e.g., open-school/local action days, citizen science activities), and through designing and exploiting science communication media (e.g., exhibitions, social media channels, and video clips).

Hundreds of students and teachers took part in science learning projects, including exploring ecosystems with our natural science backpacks in Slovenia, monitoring air pollution data in Spain, raising awareness about Antimicrobial Resistance in Cyprus, discussing how to influence political decisions about forests in Sweden, discussing ethical aspects of vaccination in Germany, and conducting a blind water tasting in Italy.

MULTIPLIERS Open Schooling Science Learning Framework

The different phases of MULTIPLIERS Teaching and Learning sequence

The theoretically and empirically rooted conceptualisation of Open Schooling guided the formulation of the framework consisting of design principles for developing and enacting a Teaching and Learning Sequence (TLS). The MULTIPLIERS framework evolves in three phases as follows:

Phase 1. Identification and exploration of socio-scientific issues (SSIs) of relevance to the local community

This is the preparation phase in which the teaching and learning activities are developed in collaboration with teachers, students and the wider OSC network. Teaching is oriented towards the socio-scientific topics to raise awareness of the issue(s), to foster students' interest in science, their self-efficacy in learning science and their science career awareness, as well as to develop relevant competences (e.g. argumentation, critical thinking) and to organize the OSS learning project.

Phase 2: Engagement in the open-school science (OSS) learning project

In this phase, students explore the SSI relevant to the local community, engage in the

OSS learning project to address the selected SSI, elaborate on the local challenges to be addressed, and collaborate with OSC members to co-create solutions and build knowledge based on sustained inquiry. Students are actively engaged in authentic activities and scientific practices by interacting with experts in school and out-of-school settings. They learn about different perspectives, engage in decision-making processes and use evidence in their argumentation.

Phase 3. Students acting as multipliers

In the final phase, the students act as multipliers, passing on their knowledge and communicating science to a wider audience through open schooling events (e.g. science fairs, poster exhibitions, community debates, video clips).

The MULTIPLIERS open schooling science learning framework covers all the educational activities that take place before, during and after the implementation of OSS learning projects. It is important to note that the duration of the teaching and learning sequences can vary from a few weeks to several months, depending on the OSS learning project, the flexibility of the stakeholders involved, the school curriculum, the timetable and the school organisation in general. MULTIPLIERS project has shown that teachers and schools in different countries have successfully adapted the framework to their local conditions. This is a key message regarding the flexibility and applicability of the teaching and learning approach in different national and regional contexts.

Active participation of students

The active participation of students is a main feature in this collaboration. Students engage in scientific practices and develop their OSS learning projects in collaboration with their teachers and science experts in an authentic environment (MULTIPLIERS Phases 1 and 2) and organise different types of open schooling events to share their projects and knowledge with their families and the wider community (Phase 3). In this phase, the students act as knowledge multipliers and are supported by the OSC members raising awareness on the socio-scientific topic to a wider audience within their community.

Conclusion

The MULTIPLIERS project offers insights to inform the design of open-schooling teaching and learning activities providing practical recommendations for curriculum design and classroom practices to enrich the curricula and pedagogical approaches in school science. We demonstrated that collaboration within the OSCs, along with the focus on active student involvement and participation, enhances the potential of school science education by broadening its scope to address socially relevant issues. This approach not only enhances students' interest in science and awareness about science careers, but also strengthens their critical thinking and argumentation skills, preparing them to engage with complex societal challenges more effectively.

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Open Schooling Science learning projects foster students' interest in science, ownership of their learning and science career awareness

Authors: MULTIPLIERS consortium

The MULTIPLIERS project builds on the strengths of an international consortium of eight beneficiaries and aims to initiate a process that helps schools to transform themselves into innovative hubs for new ideas, practices and scientific approaches. The project aims to create spaces in the communities where the beneficiaries promote open, inclusive and inquiry-based learning on complex socio-scientific issues that impact citizens' daily lives. This has been achieved by establishing partnerships ("Open Science Communities") that bring together schools, families, civil society organizations, informal education providers, policymakers, media, industry and a wide range of scientific institutions across six diverse EU countries— Cyprus, Germany, Italy, Slovenia, Spain and Sweden—each with different geographical and economic contexts.

The aim of the MULTIPLIERS project was to evaluate implemented methodologies and approaches. The policy brief summarizes the main outcomes of two implementation phases based on the MULTIPLIERS common approach described in Policy Brief 2. In this sense, this policy brief describes the main results, successful methodologies and approaches gained from the MULTIPLIERS educational activities to foster students' interest, self-efficacy and career awareness in science for all participating countries. Declining interest in science careers among young people is a growing problem. Interest in STEM careers declines with age, with motivation to pursue such careers influenced by factors such as interest, pay and the variety of career opportunities. Conversely, the barriers to STEM careers are often lack of interest or alternative career plans. The analysis of OECD results from PISA shows that students perform better in science when teachers use strategies such as teacher support or inquiry-based teaching. This is also reflected in career decisions, as students' future expectations in science are positively related to their performance and enjoyment of the subject (1,2).

Interest in science

The MULTIPLIERS project has identified several successful methodologies and approaches for fostering students' interest in science by experiencing and engaging in scientific activities conducted at the OSC-partners' sites. Key findings show that the

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Students showed interest in science:

"I definitely recommend it. It was a lot of fun, and it's just completely different from a regular lesson." (Student, Germany)

"To visit professional labs where scientist are working is something that students usually remember even long after." (Teacher, Spain)

"The students found the research very exciting, and they asked if we could visit them again to see more of their research." (Teacher, Sweden)

"Usually there are a few girls who never participate in the class debates and explain their own ideas, surprisingly today, most of them contributed with their ideas." (Teacher, Cyprus)

project enabled a consistent emphasis on hands-on and inquiry-based learning in authentic and real-world contexts, on involving experts and the community, on allowing space for student autonomy and responsibility, on working in groups, and on interdisciplinary and creative approaches to stimulate and sustain student interest.

Self-efficacy

The project also identified several successful methodologies and approaches for fostering self-efficacy among students. The project used a multifaceted approach that incorporates autonomy, authentic learning experiences, peer interactions and inquiry-based methods. These strategies not only build students' confidence in their abilities of being knowledge multipliers and how they should position themselves among other, but also prepare them to actively participate in addressing real-world challenges in their communities.

Science career awareness

The common strategies employed by the different partners emphasize the importance of direct interaction with professionals, experiential learning and exposure to very relevant, societal challenges in real-world work environments. Students get to meet or know experts that are contributing to face pressing complex socio-scientific issues. Together, these approaches enhance students' understanding of different careers, particularly in the sciences. These strategies not only inform students about possible careers, but also inspire and motivate them to explore these paths further.

Conclusion

As part of the MULTIPLIERS project, various partners have implemented a range of methodologies and approaches to foster students' interest, self-efficacy and career awareness in science. The common thread across these diverse initiatives is the engagement of students with real-world, local socio-scientific issues, experts and authentic information, which collectively contribute to the development of these essential skills such as critical thinking and argumentation. This improves students' ability to make informed decisions in different contexts.

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Students showed Self-efficacy

"I liked many things about the project, but most of all: expressing my knowledge to someone I don't know and conveying my passion." (Student, Italy)

"Working with the software was a bit difficult at first, but once we understood it, it was quite good." (Student, Germany)

"I was amazed at the students' poise in explaining the activities to people both younger and older than themselves." (Teacher, Slovenia)

Science career awareness

"What I liked most about the expert was to see how interested she was in this area and how she explained it with a sparkle in her eyes. She encouraged me to pursue a career." (Student, Slovenia)

"Contact with the working world gives me a greater understanding of what attracts me as a post-high school pathway." (Student, Italy)

"I had a different picture of science careers. I thought that being a scientist meant being cooped up in a lab and doing experiments all day which I found very boring, but it has nothing to do with reality. It is interesting!" (Student, Cyprus)

Building and Sustaining Open Schooling Networks: Ensuring Long-term Impact of Collaborative Science Education

Authors: MULTIPLIERS consortium

The EU Horizon 2020 project MULTIPLIERS aims to improve science learning by fostering collaboration among students, schools, families, local communities, civil society organizations, informal learning providers, universities, the media, policymakers, and industry. To achieve this, the project transformed educational settings into innovative Open Schooling Communities (OSCs). MULTIPLIERS has established OSCs across six EU countries, promoting partnerships between schools, society, and scientific institutions. These networks have successfully addressed socio-scientific issues and increased student engagement with science.

As the project advances, sustaining these networks long-term is now a priority. This policy brief highlights key strategies for policymakers and educators to maintain and expand open schooling initiatives. Based on extensive research and collaboration, MULTIPLIERS developed a sustainability model offering a roadmap for

creating engaging, relevant, and lasting open schooling experiences, contributing to a more scientifically literate society.

The MULTIPLIERS project has demonstrated the effectiveness of Open Schooling Communities in addressing socio-scientific issues and enhancing student engagement with science. These networks provide authentic learning experiences, improve science literacy, and foster critical thinking skills. Sustaining such networks is essential for the continuous improvement of science education, long-term community engagement in scientific issues, and nurturing future generations of scientists and informed citizens.

To address the challenge of long-term viability, MULTIPLIERS has developed the “5 Co”-Model, a comprehensive framework that identifies five key factors crucial for the sustainability of open schooling networks:

- 1. Communication:** Establishing clear channels for information sharing. This encompasses a range of strategies and interactions designed to foster engagement, collaboration, and inclusivity among all stakeholders involved in the project and beyond.
- 2. Coordination:** Ensuring effective management of partnerships and resources. In addition to formal organization, the composition of the network and the different needs of the individual partners have to be considered to foster strong partnerships.
- 3. Cooperation:** Enhancing collective impact through structured operations, effective mapping, and strategic collaboration. This involves mutual support and shared responsibilities of partners.
- 4. Costs:** Addressing financial sustainability through various funding mechanisms. This comprises both external financial support and internal funding opportunities.
- 5. Collection of Materials:** Developing and maintaining a repository of resources and best practices. This includes providing accessible, relevant, and customizable educational materials, along with ongoing support for educators.

This model provides a structured approach to building resilient and effective open schooling networks. By focusing on these five areas, Open Schooling Communities can create a strong foundation for long-term success and impact.

The benefits of implementing this sustainability model are numerous. For students, it ensures continued access to engaging, real-world science experiences that enhance their learning and career aspirations. Educators benefit from ongoing professional development and support in delivering innovative science education. Communities gain from increased scientific literacy and engagement with local issues. Researchers benefit from enhanced science communication, broader impact and societal contribution and opportunities for developing the next generation of scientists. Policymakers can leverage these networks to address societal challenges and promote evidence-based decision-making.

Figure 1: The “5 Co” Sustainability Model

Key Insights from the MULTIPLIERS “5 Co”-Model for Sustainable Networks

- 1. Communication:** Engage regularly with network members through diverse activities to keep everyone informed. Use clear, appropriate language for different stakeholders to ensure effective communication.
- 2. Coordination:** Promote diversity and establish local partnerships to leverage community insights, aligning the project with local needs. Implement clear management structures and develop a strategic plan aligned with national education goals.
- 3. Collaboration:** Encourage active participation through transparency and defined roles. Cultivate a culture of peer feedback and involve all stakeholders—students, teachers, parents, industry partners, and policymakers—in decision-making. Include experts, such as those in science education, to help bridge gaps and enhance the collaborative effort.
- 4. Costs:** Secure financial stability by using varied funding strategies, including public-private partnerships and grants, to support the network’s sustainability.
- 5. Collection of Materials:** Ensure easy access to educational materials and provide ongoing teacher training to equip educators with the skills to effectively utilise and adapt these resources.

Key Recommendations for Policymakers

To support the establishment and the sustainability of open schooling networks, policymakers should consider the following actions:

- **Establish dedicated funding streams:** Create specific funding mechanisms to support the ongoing operations of open schooling networks. This includes grants for educational outreach and professional development.
- **Develop supportive policies:** Encourage research institutions and industries to collaborate with schools by providing frameworks that promote resource allocation for these initiatives.
- **Encourage cross-sector collaboration:** Create spaces where scientists, educators, and policymakers can meet, exchange ideas, and develop new approaches to science education.
- **Recognise and reward participation:** Establish incentives for schools, teachers, and partners who actively engage in open schooling initiatives.
- **Align school curricula with the needs of modern science education:** Integrate contemporary scientific challenges (e.g., climate change, health issues) into educational programs and ensure that students engage in hands-on, real-world science education.
- **Promote professional development:** Provide continuous training for educators enabling them to effectively deliver innovative science education in collaboration with researchers.
- **Support digital infrastructure:** Invest in platforms and tools that enable efficient communication and resource development and sharing among open schooling networks and facilitate remote collaboration between schools and research institutions.

Conclusion

The sustainability of open schooling networks is crucial for the long-term transformation of science education and societal engagement with scientific issues. The “5 Co”-model developed through the MULTIPLIERS project provides a comprehensive framework for ensuring the longevity and effectiveness of Open Schooling Communities. By focusing on Communication, Coordination, Cooperation, Costs, and Collection of Materials, stakeholders can build resilient networks that continue to thrive beyond initial funding periods.

Policymakers play a vital role in creating a fertile environment for these initiatives to flourish. By establishing dedicated funding streams, and developing supportive policies, they can lay the groundwork for sustainable science education transformation. Educators and community partners, must be supported in implementing open schooling, fostering a culture of collaboration and continuous improvement.

As we look to the future of science education, the lessons learned from the MULTIPLIERS project and the implementation of the “5 Co”-Model offer a roadmap for creating engaging, relevant, and sustainable open schooling experiences. By investing in these networks, we invest in a more scientifically literate, critically thinking, and engaged citizenry, better equipped to address the complex challenges of our time.

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